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PHYSICAL AND BIOPHARMACEUTICAL PROPERTIES OF QUERCETIN EMULGELS FOR DERMAL DRUG DELIVERY

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Natural flavonoid quercetin is widely present in fruits and vegetables. It is a lipophilic compound that exerts various pharmacological effects such as anticancer, antiinflammatory, antioxidation, antianemic, antiplatelet, hypolipidemic and cardioprotective action. Emulgels (emulsion gels) are semisolid dosage forms which consist of a mixture of emulsion and gel, used for dermal delivery of lipophilic drug substances such as quercetin. Nowadays emulsion gel formulations are commonly used because they are easy to use, which enhances patient compliance. Physical characteristics of emulgels depend on proper selection of oil phase, emulsifier and gelling agent. The objective was to formulate a quercetin emulsion gel for topical application with satisfactory physical properties and to examine the influence of gelling agent, oil phase and emulsifier on the emulsion gel characteristics. Eight emulsion gel formulations containing 0.5% quercetin were prepared with concentrations of carbomer 940 as a gelling agent of 0.25% and 0.75%, concentrations of castor oil as an oil phase of 10% and 20%, and concentrations of Tween[®] 20/Span[®] 20 mixture (1:2) as an emulsifier of 1.5% and 3%. Emulgels were evaluated for their physical appearance, type of emulsion, pH, spreadability, occlusive properties, quercetin content and its release from formulations. The prepared emulgels had soft creamy consistency, homogenous texture, shiny appearance and favorable tactile properties. Quercetin emulsion gels contained O/W type of emulsion with variable homogeneity and consistency, but all having adequate pH values (6.3-6.5) and quercetin contents (0.50-0.52%). The proportion of gelling agent was the predominant factor in determining the spreadability and the release of quercetin from the formulation. Emulgels exerted mild to moderate occlusive effect and the concentration of oil phase had the greatest impact on occlusivity, although the other components contributed as well. In conclusion, the formulation composition significantly affects the physical characteristics of quercetin emulsion gels. Emulgel with 0.75% gelling agent, 10% oil phase and 1.5% emulsifier can be considered as the optimal quercetin formulation for dermal delivery.

Keywords: Emulsion gel, Drug release, Quercetin, Occlusion, Drug content.

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